

THE EFFECT OF OTOTOXICITY ON THE AUDITORY SYSTEM (PART II): DIAGNOSIS, MONITORING, AND STRATEGIES TO PREVENT HEARING LOSS.

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In this bulletin, we continue with a topic important to the long-term health of the hearing system: ototoxicity. We recommend you first read a previous outline on ototoxic substances, hearing loss, vulnerable groups, and clinical implications (part I, published in September 2025). This newsletter sets out further considerations about ototoxicity.

DIAGNOSIS AND MONITORING OF OTOTOXICITY

A number of international researchers have warned of an important problem relating to ototoxicity, which is the long delay between ingestion of an ototoxic substance and diagnosis of a resulting hearing loss.

Hearing loss induced by ototoxicity generally evolves slowly and silently, going unnoticed in many cases and only being identified when significant difficulties in communication emerge – a decline in hearing and problems understanding speech, situations which can be further compromised by environmental noise.

The occurrence of hearing loss due to ototoxicity cannot be predicted by the treatment regimen, the daily dose of medication, or the cumulative dose. In addition, other factors such as synergy with other medications and exposure to noise, even if recreational, make it even more difficult to predict the occurrence of hearing problems. The most reliable method for detecting ototoxicity is to monitor hearing function over the course of treatment and at subsequent audiological follow-ups.

A clinical diagnosis of ototoxicity involves comparing audiological results tested before and after exposure to ototoxic substances. However, it is still rare for this procedure to be routinely carried out in patients who may have been subjected to hearing damage. That is, the lack of an audiological assessment before the start of treatment with ototoxic drugs continues to be an obstacle to diagnosing the occurrence of hearing loss. It is known, however, that approximately 40% of cancer patients treated with ototoxic drugs report some kind of hearing decline during or after treatment. Finally, the administration of ototoxic drugs is often an emergency response, as in the case of aminoglycosides, making it difficult to carry out an audiological examination before using the drug. Thus, the presence of a multidisciplinary team is important for supporting these patients.

In a recent review, only 18% of clinical oncologists reported requesting a routine audiological assessment in their treatment program.

A speech therapist or audiologist plays an extremely important role in the support team. In addition to their primary responsibility – audiological assessment – if they detect possible ototoxicity they need to inform the rest of the clinical team and, when possible, propose adjusting the dose of the drug in order to reduce the cumulative dose per treatment cycle. In addition, the speech therapist/audiologist needs to advise and guide the patient and their family: offering self-assessment scales to understand the on-going impact of hearing, balance, and communication problems on the patient's quality of life, and setting out alternative communication strategies. If permanent hearing loss is a late effect of treatment, the audiologist needs to offer rehabilitation strategies that may include selecting and fitting electronic devices (hearing aids or cochlear implants), vestibular rehabilitation, tinnitus rehabilitation, or central auditory processing rehabilitation. Based on the patient's age and stage of speech and language development, appropriate speech and language assessments and therapies may also be included in the rehabilitation.

AUDIOLOGICAL INVESTIGATION PROCEDURES FOR ASSESSING AND MONITORING OTOTOXICITY

Among the audiological investigation procedures for assessing and monitoring ototoxicity that have proven to be effective are the following:

- **Conventional pure tone audiometry:** this is the gold standard for detecting the presence of peripheral hearing loss. Hearing loss due to ototoxicity initially affects the hair cells at the basal turn of the cochlea, so hearing losses begin at high frequencies, often above 8 kHz. However, once high-frequency hearing loss has been detected, international guidelines on ototoxicity recommend monitoring changes in hearing thresholds using conventional pure tone audiometry (below 8 kHz).
- **High-frequency pure tone audiometry (HFA):** is a test to obtain hearing thresholds above the conventional range, typically between 9 and 20 kHz. This method is sensitive to early damage in the basal portion of the cochlea, the first site affected by ototoxic drugs, and can detect alterations before they appear in conventional audiometry.

However, like conventional audiometry, HFA is a subjective test that requires the patient's cooperation and may not be suitable for very young children or individuals with neurological impairments. Researchers have reported that the HFA can be used using an alternative protocol with five-frequency testing for patients exposed to cisplatin.

However, one of the difficulties encountered with the HFA is the lack of standardization of responses by frequency, and it is therefore a useful tool in the longitudinal monitoring of patients, in which the responses obtained in the same individual are compared over time.

DPOAE Analysis (Right ear)

F2, Hz	L1, dB	L2, dB	DP, dB	Noise, dB	SNR, dB	OAE
556	66.6	56.8	6.15	9.09	-2.9	✘
684	65.8	56.2	3.47	4.22	-0.8	✘
889	65.8	53.8	7.44	1.73	5.7	✘
988	65.2	54.2	5.81	-0.31	6.1	✔
1270	64.6	55.0	12.84	6.44	6.4	✔
1778	64.9	54.1	2.17	-6.06	8.2	✔
2222	64.0	55.6	-3.30	-10.23	6.9	✔
2500	64.5	54.8	-6.15	-12.96	6.8	✔
3200	64.9	55.1	-0.71	-7.52	6.8	✔
4444	65.1	55.1	6.47	-9.30	15.8	✔
5000	65.1	55.1	-4.24	-11.13	6.9	✔
6154	65.1	54.4	4.34	-5.90	10.2	✔
8000	64.2	52.8	16.62	-4.64	21.3	✔
8889	62.9	52.6	19.40	-3.70	23.1	✔
10000	63.5	51.0	6.31	-4.76	11.1	✔
11429	65.1	51.1	-8.80	-13.98	5.2	✘

Noise level (dB SPL): 60.0

DPOAE Analysis (Left ear)

F2, Hz	L1, dB	L2, dB	DP, dB	Noise, dB	SNR, dB	OAE
556	65.3	55.3	0.78	6.71	-5.9	✘
684	65.2	55.2	5.32	4.67	0.7	✘
889	65.2	55.2	8.08	1.72	6.4	✔
988	64.9	55.1	2.77	-4.58	7.4	✔
1270	65.1	55.1	5.72	-1.13	6.8	✔
1778	65.0	54.9	5.05	-7.89	12.9	✔
2222	65.1	55.0	-11.85	-14.04	2.2	✘
2500	65.0	55.3	-6.64	-14.06	7.4	✔
3200	65.4	55.3	-2.34	-9.01	6.7	✔
4444	65.3	55.2	-3.04	-10.09	7.0	✔
5000	65.2	55.1	-4.24	-10.79	6.6	✔
6154	65.1	55.1	-9.02	-16.57	7.5	✔
8000	64.8	53.4	-4.13	-10.81	6.7	✔
8889	64.2	53.8	8.77	-5.51	14.3	✔
10000	64.5	52.6	0.69	-6.16	6.9	✔
11429	65.1	55.1	-6.78	-12.93	6.1	✔

Noise level (dB SPL): 60.0

SANFINS ET AL, 2026

- **Otoacoustic emissions:** Otoacoustic emissions (OAEs) are an objective test that evaluates the function of the outer hair cells in the cochlea. There are a few types of otoacoustic emissions, such as transient otoacoustic emissions (TEOAEs), distortion product evoked otoacoustic emissions (DPOAEs), suppression otoacoustic emissions, and pressurized otoacoustic emissions.

A major advantage of OAE assessment is that it can detect cochlear alterations even when hearing thresholds are within normal limits, since the reduction in the amplitude of the emission can precede alterations in tonal hearing thresholds. For this reason, in cases of suspected ototoxicity, DPOAE testing should ideally be performed up to 12 kHz, reflecting the frequency range preferentially affected by ototoxicity.

- **Auditory Evoked Potentials:** Auditory evoked potentials are part of a battery of objective tests that assess different parts of the auditory system. Basically, these procedures are often classified by latency values and are divided into short, medium, and long latency potentials.

Among the short latency potentials (responses elicited up to 10 ms), the Brainstem Auditory Evoked Potential (BAEP/ABR) stands out. As for the Medium Latency Auditory Evoked Potential (MLAP), responses are generated between 10 and 80 ms after the sound stimulus is presented. Finally, in the Long Latency Auditory Evoked Potential (LLAEP), responses appear after 80 ms. With the exception of the LLAEP and the P300 cognitive potential, the other tests are not affected by the patient's state of consciousness (asleep, awake, paying attention).

Each potential analyzes a specific part of the auditory system, so their use is linked to the system's function. In cases of ototoxicity, we strongly recommend analyzing the data in terms of sensitivity and noting limitations of the methods for assessing the peripheral and central auditory systems as developed by Sanfins et al., 2025.

OAE Analysis (Right ear)

Stimul, dB	85,6
Stim. stab., %	99,8
A&B average, dB	15,8
A-B average, dB	5,52
Response, dB	15,7
Reproducibility, %	95,6
Noise level, dB SPL	99,3

OAE Analysis (Left ear)

Stimul, dB	85,8
Stim. stab., %	99,5
A&B average, dB	13,2
A-B average, dB	1,35
Response, dB	13,1
Reproducibility, %	96,8
Noise level, dB SPL	99,3

OAE Frequencies (Right ear)

Freq. kHz	1	2	3	4	5
Repr. %	97,8	96,3	97,5	89,7	66,5
Signal, dB	13	9,8	6,2	-4,7	-17
Noise, dB	-3,3	-3,5	-8,9	-14	-20
SNR, dB	16	13	15	9,4	3,0
OAE	✓	✓	✓	✓	

OAE Frequencies (Left ear)

Freq. kHz	1	2	3	4	5
Repr. %	97,9	97,4	87,6	91,3	43,1
Signal, dB	9,7	7,2	-1,7	-4,1	-19
Noise, dB	-6,9	-8,5	-10	-14	-17
SNR, dB	17	16	8,5	10	-1,3
OAE	✓	✓	✓	✓	

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Auditory evoked potentials can be performed when there is no possibility of behavioral assessment or when you want to study central auditory effects (neurotoxicity).

SCALES FOR CLASSIFYING THE DEGREE OF OTOTOXICITY

One of the difficulties in consistently determining the incidence of hearing loss due to ototoxicity is the use of different classification systems. This can lead to an underestimation of severity of these cases and may miss the opportunity to intervene and provide rehabilitation.

The most widespread and widely used classification scheme is that proposed by the American Speech-Language-Hearing Association (ASHA). This classification method provides for:

Grade 1: Worsening of 20 dB or more at any frequency tested.

Grade 2: Worsening of 10 dB at two adjacent frequencies.

Grade 3: Absence of responses at three consecutive frequencies in which there was previously a response.

Other proposals for classifying the degree of ototoxicity include that of the American National Cancer Institute's CTCAE, which stands for Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (version 5), which provides four degrees of classification for both hearing loss and tinnitus. Another proposed classification, TUNE, which is suitable for the adult population (see Table 1), also has four grades, with a subdivision for grades 1 and 2 (grades 1A and 1B and grades 2A and 2B). When specifically considering the pediatric population, in addition to the ASHA proposal, there is the Brock classification.

The application of the THI (Tinnitus Handicap Inventory) self-assessment questionnaire, which determines the impact of tinnitus complaints on the patient's quality of life, has also been indicated in this population, since tinnitus can be a complaint regardless of the presence of hearing loss.

TABLE 1. PROPOSALS FOR CLASSIFYING THE DEGREE OF OTOTOXICITY

	GRADE 1	GRADE 2	GRADE 3	GRADE 4
ASHA	20 dB worsening at any frequency tested	10 dB worsening at any two adjacent frequencies	Absence of response at three consecutive frequencies where there was previously a response	Not foreseen
CTCAE	Adults on monitoring - 15-25 dB change in two contiguous frequencies in at least one ear Adults without monitoring - hearing complaint in the absence of documented hearing loss	Adults under monitoring - change of 1 to >25 dB in two contiguous frequencies in at least one ear Adults without monitoring: hearing loss without indication for rehabilitation limitation in daily track activity (DTA)	Adults under monitoring - change of 1 to >25 dB in three contiguous frequencies in at least one ear; need for intervention Adults without monitoring: hearing loss with indication for rehabilitation limitation in DTA and self-care	Hearing loss up to profound (thresholds >80 dB HL) from 2 kHz. No useful hearing
TUNE	Grade 1A: change ≥ 10 dB at 8, 10, 12.5 kHz or hearing complaints, without hearing loss Grade 1B change ≥ 10 dB at 1-2-4 kHz	Grade 2A: change ≥ 20 dB at 8, 10, 12.5 kHz Grade 2B change ≥ 20 dB at 1-2-4 kHz	Threshold ≥ 35 dB at 1-2-4 kHz	Threshold ≥ 70 dB at 1-2-4 kHz

Legend: ASHA - American Speech, Hearing Association; CTCAE - Common Criteria for Adverse Events; AVD - Activities of Daily Living

In a recent article, Koot et al. (2025) proposed a new tool for classifying the degree of ototoxicity based not only on comparing hearing thresholds during monitoring, but also considering in an integrated way the patient’s complaints and presence of tinnitus. This classification system provides for classification into four grades, with grade 0 corresponding to the absence of hearing loss and tinnitus, and grade 4 in which the hearing threshold is 70 dB or worse or with the presence of tinnitus classified as catastrophic by the THI.

SENSIBILIDADE E LIMITAÇÕES DOS MÉTODOS DE AVALIAÇÕES DO SISTEMA AUDITIVO PERIFÉRICO E CENTRAL (Sanfins et al, 2025)

Evaluation method	Structures evaluated	Objective or subjective procedure	Limitations of the procedure	Sensitivity for early identification of ototoxicity
Brainstem Auditory Evoked Potential	Auditory nerve, cochlear nuclei, superior olivary complex, lateral lemniscus	Objective	Less sensitive to cochlear damage	HIGH
Conventional tonal audiometry	Auditory afferent pathways, cochlear tonotopy	Subjective	Initial hearing loss occurs at high frequencies	LOW
DPOAE	Outer Hair Cells	Objective	Can be affected by outer ear and middle ear problems	HIGH
Electrocochleography	Inner hair cells, outer hair cells, auditory nerve, auditory nerve	Objective	The procedure can be uncomfortable for the patient	HIGH
Frequency Following Response	Neural elements in the rostral brainstem, lateral lemniscus, inferior colliculus, primary and secondary auditory cortex	Objective	Analyzing this procedure requires specialized knowledge, especially in frequency domain analysis	LOW
High Frequency Audiometry	Auditory afferent pathways, cochlear tonotopy	Subjective	Requires patient cooperation, less reliable in very young/disabled patients	AVERAGE

Ipsilateral and Contralateral Acoustic Reflexes	Stapedius muscle reflex arc	Objective	Not searched at high frequencies, beyond 4 kHz	LOW
Long Latency Auditory Evoked Potentials	Thalamic projections and supratemporal auditory cortex, frontal lobe, hippocampus	Objective	In the case of the P300 cognitive potential assessment, it depends on the active participation of the patient. For this, certain processes such as auditory discrimination, attention, focus, and decision-making are essential	AVERAGE especially when monitoring patients at risk of ototoxicity, as it can identify alterations not identified by conventional tests.
Medium Latency Auditory Evoked Potentials	Inferior colliculus, reticular formation, thalamocortical pathway, medial geniculate body, area of the primary auditory cortex, and Heschl's gyrus.	Objective	It requires specialized knowledge and appropriate techniques for collection and analysis	AVERAGE especially when monitoring patients at risk of ototoxicity, as it can identify alterations not identified by conventional tests.
Speech Audiometry	Afferent and efferent auditory pathways	Subjective	Researched under ideal listening conditions	LOW
TOAE	Outer Hair Cells	Objective	It can be affected by problems in the outer and middle ear. Cannot analyze high frequencies	LOW gains prominence when used in conjunction with other procedures (crosschecking).
Tympanometry	Tympano-ossicular system	Objective	Evaluates exclusively the physiology of the middle ear	LOW gains prominence when used in conjunction with other procedures (crosschecking)

PREVENTING OTOTOXICITY

Prevention of ototoxicity is crucial, especially in vulnerable groups (for more information on vulnerable groups for ototoxicity we recommend reading the bulletin - part I).

Strategies to minimize risk include avoiding the use of ototoxic medications when safe alternatives are available, using the lowest effective dose for the shortest time necessary, and considering non-ototoxic medication alternatives whenever possible.

ADDITIONAL RECOMMENDATIONS CAN BE PROVIDED FOR EACH VULNERABLE GROUP, SUCH AS:

- **Individuals with renal insufficiency:** It is essential to adjust the dose of ototoxic drugs and monitor serum levels to avoid drug accumulation. In individuals with kidney disease, managing underlying conditions such as diabetes and hypertension, which are risk factors for both kidney disease and hearing loss, is essential.

- **Newborns, infants, and the elderly:** Careful monitoring of kidney function and avoidance of prolonged use of aminoglycosides, where possible, are crucial. Slow administration of loop diuretics can help prevent serum concentration peaks, reducing the risk of ototoxicity.
- **Workers exposed to noise and ototoxic chemicals:** Protection against exposure to loud noises is essential and must be constant, especially during treatment with ototoxic drugs. In work environments, the implementation of control measures to reduce exposure to noise and ototoxic chemicals, especially with collective measures, is essential. The adoption of individual measures such as the provision and proper use of personal protective equipment (PPE) are also important preventive measures.

MANAGING RISK FACTORS

IT IS EXTREMELY IMPORTANT FOR HEALTHCARE PROFESSIONALS TO BE AWARE OF IDENTIFYING AND MINIMIZING RISK FACTORS THAT CAN EXACERBATE OTOTOXICITY:

- **Avoid, whenever possible and safely, the simultaneous use of multiple ototoxic drugs** (e.g. aminoglycosides + loop diuretics or cisplatin) due to the risk of side-effects such as ototoxicity.
- **Monitoring kidney function closely (once a day) and adjusting the dosage as necessary** (e.g. aminoglycosides) has been shown to reduce the risk of ototoxicity compared to traditional multiple daily dosing.
- **Ensure adequate hydration** and correct electrolyte imbalances.
- In patients with pre-existing hearing loss, **consider alternative therapies if possible.**
- **Have a speech therapist or audiology specialist on the team**, both to carry out hearing monitoring, but also to advise and guide patients on communication strategies during all stages of treatment.

PREVENTION AND HEARING PROTECTION STRATEGIES

Despite the importance of hearing, the number of therapies and strategies to reverse or prevent hearing loss is still limited compared to therapies for other sense organs such as vision. Yet prevention is of fundamental importance.

In order to avoid the implications of exposure to ototoxicants, some important measures should be considered and implemented, such as:

- **Avoid or reduce exposure to loud noise:** Use earplugs in noisy environments and avoid being near loud sound sources.
- **Use ototoxic drugs with caution:** Consult a doctor before using drugs that could affect hearing and inform them of any existing hearing problems.
- **Control exposure to chemicals:** Use appropriate personal protective equipment when handling chemicals and follow safety guidelines.

OTOPROTECTIVE AGENTS

Some agents are being studied or used with limited evidence to protect the inner ear, such as:

- Sodium thiosulfate (STS): has been shown to reduce cisplatin-induced hearing loss, particularly in children. Pedmarqsi is a recently approved oncology drug designed to protect children and adolescents (ages 1 month to 17 years) from hearing loss caused by cisplatin chemotherapy. Pedmarqsi contains STS, which acts as a chelating agent. It binds to cisplatin in the bloodstream, forming inactive complexes that are excreted before they reach toxic levels in the inner ear. This helps to reduce the risk of permanent hearing loss (ototoxicity) caused by cisplatin, which can develop during treatment or even years afterwards.

Clinical trials have shown that adding sodium thiosulfate to cisplatin:

- **Reduces the risk of permanent hearing loss by 42–48%.**
- **In a pivotal clinical trial (in hepatoblastoma), the incidence of ototoxicity was reduced by 42% with the use of STS.**
- **In another trial (in various pediatric cancers), hearing loss was reduced by 48%.**

MODIFY OR DISCONTINUE THERAPY IF NECESSARY

If early signs of ototoxicity are detected, consider:

1. Reducing and adjusting the dose;
2. Increasing dosing intervals (if possible, e.g., once daily using aminoglycosides);
3. Modifying the medication to a less ototoxic alternative;
4. Learning about otoprotectants;
5. Discontinuing therapy if medically appropriate.

POST-TREATMENT MONITORING

Continue monitoring after therapy, as late effects of ototoxicity (e.g., with cisplatin) may occur up to a year after completion of treatment.

CONSIDERATIONS AND ATTENTION FOR PATIENTS AND SPECIAL POPULATIONS (INFANTS AND THE ELDERLY)

Ongoing scientific research seeks to improve hearing monitoring methods in vulnerable populations. Some of the most vulnerable populations are listed below.

- **INFANTS:**

In the United States, approximately 4 million infants are admitted to Neonatal Intensive Care Units (NICUs) each year. Prophylactic measures including various ototoxic medications are often administered.

The incidence of hearing loss in babies discharged from an NICU is 10 times higher than in babies discharged from a regular nursery. In addition to prematurity and ototoxic medications, genetic factors, as well as common clinical conditions such as hyperbilirubinemia or hypoglycemia, can also increase the risk of hearing loss in NICU infants.

Hearing loss in babies, infants, or children negatively impacts their communication skills. The degree of hearing loss impacts language development, so that the greater the loss, the greater the hearing and language impairment. Hearing monitoring of neonates and infants, particularly those with a history of NICU admission, presents significant challenges in detecting ototoxicity.

Both the American Academy of Audiology (AAA) and the American Speech-Language-Hearing Association (ASHA) emphasize the importance of establishing baseline hearing thresholds before administering medications with known ototoxic potential. This evidence-based recommendation aims to create a robust point of comparison. Obtaining baseline thresholds allows subsequent hearing assessments—performed during and after treatment—to be accurately compared, facilitating early identification of deterioration in auditory function. This approach is crucial to mitigating the adverse effects of ototoxicity and enables timely and individualized intervention.

There are specific challenges in testing the neonatal and pediatric population, including:

- **Cooperation and Test Methods:** The non-cooperative nature of babies and infants makes behavioral audiometry – the gold standard for adults – impractical. This requires reliance on electrophysiological and electroacoustic methods which, although objective, can be influenced by factors such as ambient noise, the baby's sleep state, and the presence of wax in the ear canal.
- **Vulnerability of the NICU:** Babies and infants discharged from the NICU often have multiple comorbidities, such as prematurity, low birth weight, hyperbilirubinemia, and prolonged use of mechanical ventilation, which in themselves are risk factors for hearing loss. The coexistence of these factors complicates the distinction between pre-existing hearing loss and that induced by drug ototoxicity.
- **Risk–Benefit of the Most Common Ototoxic Drugs:** In the NICU, aminoglycoside antibiotics (e.g. gentamicin, amikacin) and loop diuretics (e.g. furosemide) are often used to treat severe infections and cardiac or renal conditions. All these are known to be ototoxic. The clinical need for often life-saving drugs must be balanced against the risk of hearing damage, making monitoring essential.
- **Progression of Hearing Loss:** Ototoxicity-induced hearing loss can have an insidious onset and gradual progression, making it difficult to detect in routine assessments, especially if baseline tests have not been rigorously established. In addition, hearing loss can manifest itself late, months after exposure to the ototoxic agent.

- **Long-term consequences:** Undetected or untreated hearing loss in neonates and infants can have devastating impacts on the development of language, speech, and cognitive skills, as well as on the child's socio-emotional well-being.

- **ELDERLY PEOPLE:**

The elderly population is particularly vulnerable to the effects of drug-induced ototoxicity, which adds a layer of complexity to the already existing challenges in monitoring hearing. Various physiological, pharmacological, and socio-environmental factors contribute to this greater susceptibility and to difficulties in managing their hearing loss. By aggravating presbycusis or inducing new hearing loss, ototoxicity in the elderly has a significant impact on quality of life.

There are specific difficulties in the elderly:

- **Polypharmacy and Drug Interactions:** Elderly people often use multiple drugs to treat various chronic conditions. Polypharmacy exponentially increases the risk of drug interactions, some of which can potentiate ototoxicity. Coadministration of two or more ototoxic drugs, even at doses that would be safe on their own, can result in significant damage to the auditory and vestibular systems. For example, the combination of aminoglycosides with loop diuretics (such as furosemide) is classically associated with a high risk of ototoxicity.
- **Preexisting presbycusis:** Presbycusis, or age-related sensorineural hearing loss, is a universal condition in aging. Most elderly people already have some degree of hearing loss even before they are exposed to ototoxic agents. This means that baseline hearing for many elderly people is already compromised, and any additional drug-induced damage can have a disproportionately greater impact on communication and quality of life. The conjunction of ototoxicity and presbycusis makes it more difficult to discern the etiology of hearing loss and can mask the progression of drug-induced damage.

- **Physiological changes related to ageing:**

- **Reduced renal function:** Renal clearance decreases with age, leading to the accumulation of drugs in the body. Many ototoxic drugs, such as aminoglycosides, are excreted mainly by the kidneys. Compromised kidney function in the elderly can raise serum concentrations of these drugs, increasing the risk of toxicity.
- **Vulnerability of the Inner Ear:** The natural aging process can make hair cells of the cochlea and vestibular system more susceptible to damage, including that induced by medications.
- **Difficulties communicating and reporting symptoms:** Elderly people may have difficulty perceiving and reporting symptoms of ototoxicity (tinnitus, vertigo, worsening hearing) early on.
- **Tendency to consider hearing loss or tinnitus as a "normal" part of ageing:** a factor which causes delays in seeking help.
- **Auditory rehabilitation:** In cases of ototoxicity-induced hearing loss, it is essential that there is some sort of intervention. Hearing rehabilitation is important in order that the elderly can remain active and retain their cognitive and communicative abilities. Good hearing rehabilitation will improve the quality of life and well-being of the elderly patient.

In conclusion, ototoxicity is a significant adverse effect associated with the use of certain medications and exposure to chemical products, which can result in temporary or permanent hearing and balance problems. It is therefore important that health professionals acquire information in this area, since early identification of ototoxicity and implementation of timely interventions are of great value in minimizing the impact on the patient's quality of life.

Quiz

1. According to the text, what is the most reliable method for detecting ototoxicity, considering that hearing loss due to ototoxicity usually evolves silently? According to the text, what is the most reliable method for detecting ototoxicity, considering that hearing loss due to ototoxicity usually progresses silently?

- a) Compare the treatment regimen and the cumulative dose of the medication, without conducting audiological exams.
- b) Only the clinical evaluation of communication difficulty symptoms, such as difficulty in speech comprehension.
- c) Performance of a high-frequency pure-tone audiometry (HFPTA) before treatment, without subsequent follow-up.
- d) Monitoring of auditory function during and after treatment with ototoxic substances.

2. The text describes various audiological investigation procedures. The text describes various audiological investigation procedures. Among the objective tests mentioned, which one is particularly advantageous for being able to detect cochlear changes even before the tonal hearing thresholds are altered?

- a) High-Frequency Threshold Tone Audiometry (HFTA).
- b) Otoacoustic Emissions (OAE).
- c) Auditory Brainstem Response (ABR).
- d) Conventional Pure-Tone Audiometry (PTA).

3. According to the ASHA classification for the degree of ototoxicity mentioned in the text, which of the following situations corresponds to a 'Grade 2'?

- a) Absence of responses at three consecutive frequencies where there had been a response previously.
- b) Profound hearing loss (thresholds > 80 dBHL) starting at 2kHz.
- c) Deterioration of 20 dB or more at any tested frequency.
- d) Deterioration of 10 dB in two adjacent frequencies.

4. The text discusses the vulnerability of elderly patients to ototoxicity. The text discusses the vulnerability of elderly patients to ototoxicity. Which of the following factors is NOT mentioned as a specific difficulty in the elderly population?

- a) Physiological changes, such as the reduction of kidney function.
- b) Polypharmacy and drug interactions.
- c) Tendency to consider hearing loss as a normal part of aging.
- d) Greater susceptibility to ear infections, especially in the neonatal ICU.

5. What is the main function of sodium thiosulfate (STS) as an otoprotective agent, according to the text? What is the main function of sodium thiosulfate (STS) as an otoprotective agent, according to the text?

- a) Promote the regeneration of hair cells damaged by noise exposure.
- b) Bind to cisplatin in the bloodstream to form inactive complexes that are excreted.
- c) Reduce the dose of ototoxic medications so that adjustments in renal function are not necessary.
- d) Reduce chronic tinnitus in cancer patients after treatment.

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Quiz Correct Answers

1. Correct answer: A
 2. Correct answer: B
 3. Correct answer: B
 4. Correct answer: D
 5. Correct answer: C

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